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Review Article

ACUTE ABDOMEN IN THE EMERGENCY DEPARTMENT

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Abstract:

Introduction: 7% of the patients come to the emergency department with the chief complain of acute abdominal pain. They can have minor causes, but also be due to very serious causes, which requires urgency in care and serious diagnosis and management. Acute abdominal emergencies are a big contributor to morbidity and mortality.

Aim of the work: In this study, we aim to understand the standard way to approach a case of acute abdominal pain in the emergency department.

Methodology: we conducted this review using a comprehensive search of MEDLINE, PubMed and EMBASE from January 1970 to March 2017. The following search terms were used: acute abdomen, abdominal pain management, clinical evaluation of abdominal pain, management acute abdomen

Conclusion: Acute abdomen is an extremely common presentation in the emergency department. However, it is not easy to assess, diagnose, and manage. Rate of misdiagnoses and fatalities are high; therefore, physicians should always consider all possible and start with more serious etiologies. Proper assessment and management of acute abdomen can lead to significant improvement of morbidity and mortality.

Keywords: acute abdomen, gastro intestinal emergencies, emergency evaluation

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INTRODUCTION:

In the emergency department, one of the most common patients' presentations is pain in the abdominal area. In fact, it has been estimated that of 119 million patients who present to the emergency department annually, about 7% present with abdominal pain. Therefore, it is essential that healthcare providers get proper and sufficient training to become able to assess and manage abdominal pain cases. Despite being that common, the management of acute abdomen should be done seriously, as abdominal pain could sometimes be a reflection of a serious, or even fatal, underlying condition [1]. Moreover, abdominal pain in many cases can have medicolegal issues, and poor management could lead to bad consequences on physicians in the emergency department. Sometimes, it is difficult to detect acute abdominal pain in patients. This is due to the presence of other factors that could obscure the pain, leading to a significant delay in reaching a diagnosis. This will eventually lead to severe adverse events. Therefore, it is essential for physicians to consider serious causes when they are approaching such patients. This approach can have significant effects on improving morbidity and mortality. Although diagnostic modalities have been becoming more advanced and sophisticated, with the continuous emerging of newer imaging modalities, rates of misdiagnosis of acute appendicitis have been increasing [2].

METHODOLOGY:

- Data Sources and Search terms

We conducted this review using a comprehensive search of MEDLINE, PubMed and EMBASE, from January 1970 to March 2017. The following search terms were used: acute abdomen, abdominal pain management, clinical evaluation of abdominal pain, management acute abdomen

- Data Extraction

Two reviewers have independently reviewed the studies, abstracted data and disagreements were resolved by consensus. Studies were evaluated for quality and a review protocol was followed throughout.

This study was done after approval of ethical board of King Abdulaziz University.

Assessment of Pain

Onset

It is essential for physicians to seriously consider any case that presents with a severe abdominal pain that started acutely. Focused attention should be present on vascular etiologies like the presence of an underlying aortic dissection or aortic aneurysm. Other less serious etiologies may include volvulus,

perforated ulcer, ischemia of the mesenteries, torsion, etc. All these mentioned causes could occur without the presence of a prior warning or relevant history. An important example of this is that less than half elderly patients who presented with a perforated ulcer had reported the presence of an acute abdominal pain. Other examples of this are vascular diseases of the sigmoid colon (like volvulus and ischemia) that could also present with gradual (rather than acute) pain. On the other hand, infectious and inflammatory etiologies are usually expected to have gradual course of pain [3]. Generally, any patient who suffers from an abdominal pain that awakens him from sleep could be managed and assessed seriously until serious causes are ruled out. By determining the onset of pain, the clinician will be able to know the duration of pain and assess the case accordingly.

Location

The embryological origin of visceral organs are the determinants of the exact site of pain. Generally, visceral organs are sensitive to stretch, distension, contraction, and ischemia. A pain in the epigastric region usually reflects pain originating from structures of the foregut, which include the stomach, proximal duodenum, liver, biliary system, and pancreas. On the other hand, pain in the periumbilical region reflects pain originating from the midgut, which include the distal duodenum, jejunum, ileum, the appendix, and the proximal third of the colon. Finally, pain in the suprapubic regions reflects pain originating from the structures of hindgut, which include the remaining parts of the colon, the bladder, along with pelvic genitourinary organs. When pain originates from the kidneys, aorta, or any other retroperitoneal structure, it usually radiates to the back [2].

Intensity

Usually, severe pain is a reflection of a severe etiology. However, this is not always a reliable measure, as sometimes serious etiologies can present with relatively mild pain. This occurs mainly in elderly patients [2].

Radiation and referral of pain

A classic example of neural pathways that give predicted radiation of pain is Kehr's sign. Kehr's sign is the presence of radiated shoulder pain that results from diaphragmatic irritation (from the accumulation of free blood in the intra peritoneum, inflammation or from other probable causes). Another famous example is the feeling of pain in the right scapula which reflects the presence of a biliary disease. The importance of radiation of pain also extends to reflect disease progression. Examples of this include the

continuous passage of stones in the ureter, and ongoing aortic dissection. However, it is important to keep in mind that deep structures of the musculoskeletal system are also innervated of the exact same sensory fibers of the abdominal visceral organs, making it necessary to carefully assess the musculoskeletal system of patients before a diagnosis is made [4].

Associated symptoms

It is essential to assess associated symptoms other than the abdominal pain, with putting all gathered information in context. Examples of important associated signs and symptoms include:

1. Anorexia

There is a common belief that anorexia is almost always present in patients who present with abdominal pain due to appendicitis. However, recent studies have suggested that only 68% of appendicitis cases can report anorexia. Moreover, when dealing with older patients, the prevalence of anorexia among appendicitis patients can decrease to 20% [5].

2. Vomiting:

Vomiting is one of the most common symptoms associated with abdominal case and occur in virtually all cases of acute abdomen. Generally, in surgical conditions, pain usually occurs before vomiting, with esophageal rupture from vomiting being an exception of this. Vomiting is also an important symptom in cases of complete small bowel obstruction, but it is usually absent in early disease or in partial obstruction. On the other hand, large intestines obstruction can present without vomiting. The content of vomiting (gastric or bilious content) can also be helpful in making a diagnosis. The course of the vomiting is also important in making a diagnosis; a frequent nonproductive vomiting can suggest the presence of a possible gastric volvulus. On the other hand, a repetitive nonbilious vomiting can suggest obstruction of the gastric outlet [6].

When the vomiting contains bile or blood, this should be carefully considered. For example, an infant who present with bilious vomiting should be carefully evaluated for intestinal malrotation and other serious causes. On the other hand, vomiting that contains blood usually indicates the presence of liver or gastric diseases.

The volume of the vomiting is also important. A massive vomiting of blood usually indicates a serious case like aorto-enteric fistula. Self-limited vomiting usually indicates a benign etiology like food poisoning [7].

3. Bowel symptoms:

Although diarrhea is usually a sign of benign causes

of abdominal pain, this must not justify ruling out serious diseases. An example of a serious disease that can present with diarrhea is mesenteric ischemia. Appendicitis could also sometimes present with diarrhea. A study on 1000 patients in the emergency department who presented with abdominal pain found that about 18% of them had diarrhea at presentation. Moreover, they found that younger patients who had diarrhea were found to have benign causes of their pain. On the other hand, another study has reported that up to twenty percent of patients who have large intestinal obstruction can have diarrhea [8].

Constipation and the absence of flatus can also be considered important signs in diagnosing obstruction. The presence of blood in stool with severe abdominal pain is an indicator of the possible presence of ischemia. The presence of melena can indicate bleeding from the upper gastrointestinal tract, while fresh blood can indicate the presence of bleeding from the lower gastrointestinal tract [9].

4. Other symptoms:

Abdominal pain can be the main symptom of many diseases of the genitourinary tract. Therefore, dysuria and pyuria are common symptoms that can be associated with abdominal pain. An adult male with severe abdominal pain, vomiting, and nausea can possibly have testicular torsion. Therefore, it is essential for physicians to obtain a proper thorough history of any patient who presents with abdominal pain. This history should include their sexual history, and genitourinary history [10].

Important Physical Exam to be done in Emergency Room

It is crucial of physicians in the emergency department to be aware of physical examinations that help in diagnosing abdominal diseases. It is also crucial for them to realize the limitations of these examinations. For example, all examinations used for peritonitis can have low sensitivity and specificity.

Vitals

Any abnormality in the patient's vital signs could be alarming for the presence of a serious etiology. However, this has low sensitivity, and the absence of abnormal vital signs does not necessarily mean that no serious disease is present. For example, fever is generally an indication of infections or severe systemic diseases. However, it is sometimes absent in abdominal diseases with infectious etiologies. In fact, 30% of appendicitis cases, and most acute cholecystitis cases do not present with fever [5].

Inspection, auscultation, and percussion

Inspection is a useful tool that can detect the presence of any change in the skin, any scars of prior

surgeries, caput medusa (that suggests the presence of a liver disease), hemorrhage, along with other important findings. Percussion is also important and helps distinguish between ascites and obstruction in cases of abdominal distension. On the other hand, the use of auscultation during physical examination is limited in the abdomen [4].

Palpation

Abdominal physical examination in the emergency department aims to localize points of tenderness, identify peritonitis, and detect enlarged visceral organs and structures. Sometimes, in anxious children who poorly cooperate with the physician, it is helpful to palpate using a stethoscope. Physicians are also recommended to flex the knees and hips of the patient while performing physical examination of the abdomen. This helps relax abdominal muscles, and thus detect findings [11].

The presence of localized tenderness could guide the physician the source of the pain. On the other hand, generalized tenderness poses a larger challenge to the physician during the process of determining the source of the pain. For any patient who does not have a history of appendectomy, any tenderness in the right lower quadrant should raise immediate suspicion of appendicitis. In patients who can tolerate physical examination, the spleen and liver sizes should be assessed with deep palpation and percussion. Moreover, physicians should use deep palpation and percussion to detect masses in the abdomen. For example, the presence of a tender expansible mass that pulsates is pathognomonic for abdominal aortic aneurysm and requires immediate ultrasound to establish the diagnosis. In patients who have suspected hernia, it is useful to examine the abdomen while the patient is standing [3].

Tests for peritoneal irritation

It is always important for any patient in the emergency department who presents with abdominal pain to determine if this patient has peritonitis or not. However, all physical examination methods used to detect peritonitis have relatively low sensitivity and specificity. The rebound testing, despite having these limitations, is considered to be one of the most useful tests in detecting peritonitis and appendicitis, especially in children. However, some authors still recommend against the use of this test due to being extremely painful when compared to superficial gentle palpation [12].

The sensitivity of rebound test can sometimes reach 80% in detecting peritonitis, but its specificity can be as low as 40% [13]. Other indirect tests that detect

peritonitis (like the cough test) can have similar sensitivity to the rebound test with relatively higher specificity. The “heel drop jarring” test is another indirect test for peritonitis that is specifically helpful in children [14].

The definition of guarding is made by the involuntary increase of abdominal muscles tone that reflects an attempt of the body to decrease movements of visceral structures. Voluntary guarding, on the other hand, can indicate that the patient is normal but is anxious of the abdominal physical examination. Extreme true guarding can lead to rigidity. However, both guarding and rigidity may be absent in older patients because their abdominal muscles weakness. In fact, less than 25% of patients older than 70 years who presented with perforated ulcer, had abdominal rigidity [3].

The rectal examination

The role of rectal physical examination is somewhat limited when evaluating a patient with acute abdominal pain in the emergency department. However, in cases of intestinal ischemia, colorectal malignancies and late intussusception, it can be helpful. Generally, it is not recommended to routinely perform a rectal examination in all patients who present to the emergency department with abdominal pain. This is strictly important in children, who must not have this test done unless it is significant [15].

Special abdominal examination techniques

Carnett's sign:

The presence of tenderness in the abdominal wall could be an indicator of underlying trauma. Due to the recent increase of use of anticoagulation, hematoma in the abdominal wall has also become a common cause of tenderness.

The physician should determine the maximal pain point, and then palpate it with the wall of the abdomen being both relaxed or tensed, and with the patient sitting and having arms crossed. A positive Carnett's sign means that there is more abdominal pain when the abdominal wall is tensed, whereas a negative Carnett's sign means that there is less abdominal pain when the abdominal wall is tensed. Positive Carnett's sign is considered to be a sign of pathology in the abdominal wall rather than abdominal viscera. In fact, a previous study has found that out of 120 patients with abdominal pain, 24 had Carnett's sign, and only one of these 24 had an intra-abdominal pathology, indicating the high specificity of this sign [16]. Other studies have also concluded that this sign is useful in detecting abdominal wall pathologies. The use of this test is not

routinely recommended but is done when there is a history that suggests an abdominal wall pathology [17].

Cough test:

This test was first described in 1909 by Rostovzev and aimed to detect peritoneal irritation through making the patient cough. Previous studies on this test have found that it had very high sensitivity and specificity in detecting both peritonitis and appendicitis in patients who have right lower quadrant abdominal pain [18].

Murphy's sign:

This sign is performed by stopping respiration of the patient while the examiner is putting their fingers on the right upper quadrant. This sign is very commonly used by physicians in the assessment of cholecystitis, despite having relatively low sensitivity (65%) [19].

The psoas sign:

This sign is considered positive when the patient (who lifts the thigh against resistance) have increased pain, which reflects psoas muscle irritation. When this sign is found positive on the right side, this suggests the presence of appendicitis. Other inflammatory diseases can also show positive psoas sign like pancreatitis, pyelonephritis, psoas abscess, along with other causes [20].

Obturator Sign:

Similar to the psoas sign, the presence of a positive obturator sign is an indication of the presence of an inflammation that is causing irritation to the muscles. Conditions that cause positive obturator sign include pelvic appendicitis, sigmoid diverticulitis, ectopic pregnancy, and pelvic inflammatory disease [21].

Imaging

Historically, plain abdominal X-ray was the only imaging modality present to diagnose abdominal pain in the emergency department. Plain X-rays were only indicated for less than half of the patients presenting with abdominal pain. With advances in imaging modalities, the use of plain X-ray in diagnosing acute abdomen has continued to decrease. In fact, it became only used in 21% of patients with abdominal pain in 2007. On the other hand, the use of more advanced techniques has been continuously increasing. For example, ultrasound was found to be used in up to 42% of patients with abdominal pain in 2007. Generally, the role of plain abdominal X-ray is very limited in detecting underlying causes of acute abdominal pain [22].

CT scan led to a major advance in the diagnosis and assessment of acute abdominal pain due to its ability

to provide cross-sectional slices of the body, thus allowing for accurate visualization of abdominal organs. The use of contrast media in CT further enhances its ability to detect abnormalities and visualize tissues. However, CT causes a 15-fold higher exposure to radiation than plain X-rays. This has been found to cause significant increase in cancer risk. In patients whose abdominal pain is suspected to be due to renal colic, lower doses of radiation could be used when performing CT [23].

Ultrasound remains the most common imaging modality that is currently used in the assessment of abdominal pain. This wide use of it is due to many reasons including availability, low-costs, and no exposure to radiation [24].

Approach to Unstable Patients in ED

When patients with abdominal pain present with unstable vital signs, this should be taken seriously. Mortality of acute abdomen in elderly patients with unstable vital signs is significantly high, as this instability will lead to severe complications.

These patients should be properly resuscitated with achieving sufficient airway control. When the patient has decreased blood pressure, treatment of this should be started. In such patients, the use of ultrasound is extremely important. Hypotension in older patients should raise the suspicion of aortic aneurysm, which should be detected by ultrasound. Other causes of hypotension in younger patients with abdominal pain include ruptured ectopic pregnancy, ruptured spleen, ruptured ovarian cyst, and other causes. Pregnancy test must be done in all females with this presentation [25].

Conclusion

Acute abdomen is an extremely common presentation in the emergency department. However, it is not easy to assess and manage. Moreover, some of the underlying causes can be serious or even fatal. This can sometimes lead to delayed diagnosis which will lead to severe complications and morbidities. Physicians should always consider all possible causes of acute abdomen and start with more serious etiologies. Proper assessment and management of acute abdomen can lead to significant improvement of morbidity and mortality.

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